

Chalcones. xx: Potential Germicides derived from Acetylphenanthrenes

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Seventeen new phenanthryl chalcone analogues have been prepared because of their germicidal properties. Some of the compounds have been tested for their germicidal activity against *S. aureus*.

THE present investigation has been undertaken in continuation¹⁻⁷ of the study of chalcone analogues as potential germicides and reports the preparation of seventeen 2- and 3-phenanthryl chalcone analogues for evaluating their biological activity against *S. aureus*. These were prepared from corresponding acetyl phenanthrene and aryl aldehydes in the presence of 20% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution, by the method of Misra⁷⁻⁸. The condensation with nitro and halo substituted benzaldehydes resulted into better yields than

methyl and methoxy substituted benzaldehydes whereas with hydroxy benzaldehydes it was least (Table 1).

The germicidal activity of the compounds was screened against *S. aureus* by using agar-cup method (incubation temp. $32^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$). Encouraging results were not obtained.

Table 1 lists seventeen phenanthryl chalcones alongwith their physical properties. The compounds were identified by, halochromic effect with Conc.

TABLE I

Sl.No.	Ar	R	M.P.* °C of		Yield %	Colour and crystal form	Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄
			chalcone	2 : 4-DNP			
1.	2-Phenanthryl	3 : 4-(O-CH ₂ -O)	186	213	67	Light yellow plates	red
2.	2-Phenanthryl	4-NO ₂	222	—	85	Yellow needles	red
3.	2-Phenanthryl	2 : 4-(OH) ₂	147	—	35	Buff plates	red
4.	2-Phenanthryl	2-OH-3-OMe	143	—	54	Yellow plates	blood-red
5.	2-Phenanthryl	4-OH-3-OMe	140-1	221	40	Pale needles	red
6.	2-Phenanthryl	5-NO ₂ -4-OH-3-OMe	129	—	73	Yellow needles	orange
7.	2-Phenanthryl	2-OH-5,6-Benzo	112	—	37	Golden yellow plates	yellowish brown
8.	2-Phenanthryl	2-Br	144	—	78	Yellow plates	blood-red
9.	2-Phenanthryl	2 : 6-Cl ₂	139	240	dec79	Shining needles	red
10.	2-Phenanthryl	3-NO ₂	187	—	76	Yellow globules	red
11.	2-Phenanthryl	6-Br-3 : 4(OCH ₃) ₂	143	—	65	Yellow plates	pink
12.	2-Phenanthryl	6-Br-3 : 4-(O-CH ₂ O)	211	—	63	Dull yellow globules	violet
13.	2-Phenanthryl	4-NMe ₂	146	—	57	Yellow hexagone	yellowish
14.	3-Phenanthryl	6-Br-3 : 4(OCH ₃) ₂	92	236	69	Bright yellow needles	violet
15.	3-Phenanthryl	5-Br-4-OH-3-OMe	86	—	55	Shining needles	red
16.	3-Phenanthryl	4-NMe ₂	127	208	61	Orange globules	scarlet
17.	3-Phenanthryl	5 : 6-Benzo	126	—	53	Golden plates	violete

* All melting points are uncorrected.

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H₂SO₄, preparing a few 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazon^e derivatives and elemental analyses. The chalcones and their derivatives analysed satisfactorily for

C, H and N within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical value.

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References

1. S. S. MISRA, S. C. KUSHWAHA and J. B. LAL, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, **40(A)**, 301.
2. S. S. MISRA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, **40(A)**, 468.
3. S. S. MISRA and J. B. LAL, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, **40(A)**, 296.
4. S. S. MISRA and R. S. TEWARI, *Labdev. J. Sci. & Tech.*, 1971, **9-A**, 152.
5. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 637.
6. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 639.
7. S. S. MISRA and R. S. TEWARI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, **34**, 211.
8. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, **34**, 260.